

Text Analysis Using Logistic Regression

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Abstract— Text analysis is the evaluation and categorization of a person's feelings and beliefs based on the text being studied. Text classification and machine learning are essential for sentiment analysis. That implies that we can infer or categorise people's opinions from their comments. Several machine learning techniques, such as naive Bayes, support vector machines, logistic regression, and K-nearest neighbours, are used to analyse text in this work. We suggest a few text categorization frameworks, and applying these methods on the provided datasets, we analyse the information. The experimental findings have demonstrated that our suggestions can perform better, particularly the logistic regression model, which can produce more accurate predictions.

Keywords—Pycharm, Naïve-Bayes, Support-vector-machine, Logistic regression

I. INTRODUCTION

Here various machine learning algorithms were used for text analysis. Using a machine learning technique, one input is provided in this case for text classification. Typically, text documents are used to carry out the classification based on a selection of documents and attributes. However, it's referred to as supervised machine learning operation and the classes were chosen before the experiment analysis. We need a machine learning strategy to categorise this information. Using Nave Bayes and logistic regression, in-text categorization statistical analysis is performed to give analytical and comparative research for feature selection. The accuracy is comparing using different algorithms support vector machine, knn, naive bayes, logistic regression. Analysis and test is done using the machine learning algorithm logistic regression. The user can give a review about anything such as movie, songs, books, etc. A compilation of reviews itself may be called a review. Consumer reviews for sellers and products are available separately on e-commerce websites. When writing a review of a product or service, customers typically discuss how valuable the item or service is to them and how well it lives up to the seller's specifications. Customer reviews, usually referred to as user-generated content, are quite distinct from those produced by marketers. Since the review replies in marketer-generated content are made by the marketer, the consumer must choose from any of the options offered by the marketer. The selection of effective machine learning

approaches is also covered in this study through a comparative examination. We choose the effective machine learning algorithm for our text classification through comparative analysis. Consequently, numerous text analysis. Therefore, several text analysis techniques have been proposed to automate this analysis process.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

Xiaoyu Luo et al [1] Text analysis an approach used for the classification of any kind of documents. Any type of document can be classified for the target category or not using the text classification method. The Support Vector Machines model was used in this study's classification of English text and documents. They test the chosen classifiers using English documents in two analytical tests. The Rocchio classifier performs best when the size of the feature set is small, whereas SVM beats the other classifiers, according to experimental results on a collection of 1033 text documents.

Raymond Chiong et al [2] By analysing social media texts, particularly those specific messages that contain terms like "depression" or "diagnostic," the study aims to evaluate whether the machine learning method could be utilised to detect the indicators of depression in social media users. They use some selected words defined as keywords or tokens. By using that keywords they analyse text. The study's concluding findings show that the suggested method may effectively identify sadness in social media texts even when training datasets lack specific keywords and when testing datasets are taken from unrelated domains.

Asogwa D.C et al [3] Hatred that was formerly contained to verbal communication has quickly spread across the Internet. Online discussion forums and social media sites that enable people to share their thoughts are being used as platforms for the dissemination of hate speech. Through this research, Support Vector Machine (SVM) and Nave Bayes algorithms were used to provide potential solutions for the issue of automatic hate message detection.

Pratyaksh Jain et al [4] This paper also analysis the depression of a person by analysing the suicidal comments that included in their texts. Depression is a typical mental condition that can affect functioning and cause suicidal thoughts or attempts. Machine learning and natural language processing were applied. The subedits are real online places to ask for help and give honest text data about people's mental states, according to a quick perusal of the articles. We have

employed a variety of ML methods, including SVM and Naive Bayes.

V.K. Singh et al[5] This article presents the experimental results along with the performance of all three techniques for document-level sentiment categorization. using two massive, pre-existing datasets, one that we independently obtained that was of a considerable size, and two others.Both a new modified Adjective plus Adverb combination scheme of the SentiWordNet technique and a full analysis of the effectiveness of each of the three approaches when combined with movie reviews comprise the key contributions.

III. METHOD OF PREDICTION

Data plays an important role in Text analysis. The required dataset is collected from Kaggle and the data from movies. The process consists of two phases:

Training phase: During the first phase, also known as the training phase, the system is trained using the dataset's data and a model that is fitted using the selected algorithm.

Testing phase: Consisting of the second phase the system is fed inputs and checked to ensure that it works properly.. Different algorithms were used to check the accuracy before they were chosen for test. The best one is finally selected for the analysis.

Figure 1:Sample Data

```

1 The Da Vinci Code book is just awesome.
1 this was the first clive cussler I've ever read, but even books like Relic, and Da Vinci code were n
1 I liked the Da Vinci Code a lot.
1 I liked the Da Vinci Code a lot.
1 I liked the Da Vinci Code but it ultimately didn't seem to hold it's own.
1 that's not even an exaggeration ) and at midnight we went to Wal-Mart to buy the Da Vinci Code, whic
1 I loved the Da Vinci Code, but now I want something better and different!..
1 I thought da vinci code was great, same with kite runner.
1 The Da Vinci Code is actually a good movie...
1 I thought the Da Vinci Code was a pretty good book.
1 The Da Vinci Code is one of the most beautiful movies ive ever seen.
1 The Da Vinci Code is an * amazing * book, do not get me wrong.
1 then I turn on the light and the radio and enjoy my Da Vinci Code.
1 The Da Vinci Code was REALLY good.
1 I love da vinci code....

0 Da Vinci Code sucked..
0 The Da Vinci Code sucked big time.
0 Da Vinci Code = Up, Up, Down, Down, Left, Right, Left, Right, B, A, SUCK!
0 by the way, the Da Vinci Code sucked, just letting you know...
0 I heard da vinci code sucked soo much only 2.5 stars:
0 da vinci code sucks...
0 Da Vinci Code sucks.
0 friday hung out with kelsie and we went and saw The Da Vinci Code SUCKED!!!!
0 Combining the opinion / review from Gary and Gin Zen, The Da Vinci Code sucks.
0 Da Vinci Code sucks be...
    
```

A. Techniques Used

- Model with the greatest accuracy:

Here, we chose the machine learning technique with the highest accuracy out of four that we considered.

Figure 2: Testing the best performance model

```

Naive Bayes
Accuracy Score: 98.91618497109826%
Confusion Matrix:
[[586 12]
 [ 3 783]]

Logistic Regression
Accuracy Score: 99.34971098265896%
Confusion Matrix:
[[593 5]
 [ 4 782]]

Support Vector Machine
Accuracy Score: 99.0606936416185%
Confusion Matrix:
[[592 6]
 [ 7 779]]

K Nearest Neighbors (NN = 3)
Accuracy Score: 98.69942196531792%
Confusion Matrix:
[[589 9]
 [ 9 777]]
    
```

- Logistic Regression

For categorization and predictive analytics, this statistical model, commonly referred to as the logistic model, is frequently utilized. By using logistic regression, one may calculate the likelihood that an event will occur. The dependent variable is restricted to the range between 0 and 1 since the outcome requires probability. In logistic regression, the odds—i.e., the likelihood of success divided by the probability of failure—are subjected to a logistic transformation.

Figure 3:Analysing Data

```

trainingVector = CountVectorizer(stop_words='english', ngram_range = (1,1), max_df = .80, min_df = 5)
trainingVector.fit(X)
X_dtm = trainingVector.transform(X)
LR_complete = LogisticRegression()
LR_complete.fit(X_dtm, y)

#Input Review
print("\nTest a custom review message")
print("Enter review to be analysed: ", end=" ")
test = []
test.append(input())
test_dtm = trainingVector.transform(test)
predLabel = LR_complete.predict(test_dtm)
tags = ['Negative', 'Positive']
#Display Output
print("The review is predicted", tags[predLabel[0]])
    
```

IV. RESULT

After we train the data we need to set tokens that tokens will set using naive bayes algorithm ,after completely analysing our dataset set some selective words are tokens using this algorithm.While we enter a text it analysis based on the tokens and predicted positive or negative. The dataset is first loaded after which data within the dataset are trained and tested.

Figure 4:Setting Tokens using naïve bayes

```
#Naive Bayes Analysis
tokens_words = vect.get_feature_names()
print('\nAnalysis')
print('No. of tokens: ',len(tokens_words))
counts = NB.feature_count
df_table = {'Token':tokens_words,'Negative': counts[0,:],'Positive': counts[1,:]}
tokens = pd.DataFrame(df_table, columns= ['Token','Positive','Negative'])
positives = len(tokens[tokens['Positive']])
print('No. of positive tokens: ',positives)
print('No. of negative tokens: ',len(tokens_words)-positives)
#Check positivity/negativity of specific tokens
token_search = ['awesome']
print('\nSearch Results for token/s:',token_search)
print(tokens.loc[tokens['Token'].isin(token_search)])
#Analyse False Negatives (Actual: 1; Predicted: 0)(Predicted negative review for a positive review)
print(X_test[y_pred < y_test])
#Analyse False Positives (Actual: 0; Predicted: 1)(Predicted positive review for a negative review)
print(X_test[y_pred > y_test])
```

After we set tokens using naive bayes algorithm next step is to analyse the review using the best performing model. This can be done using the logistic regression. Logistic regression estimates the probability of an event occurring.

Figure 5:Analysing and testing using Logistic regression

```
#Naive Bayes Analysis
trainingVector = CountVectorizer(stop_words='english', ngram_range=(1,1), max_df=.80, min_df=.5)
trainingVector.fit(X)
X_dtm = trainingVector.transform(X)
LR_complete = LogisticRegression()
LR_complete.fit(X_dtm, y)
#Input Review
print('\nTest a custom review message')
print('Enter review to be analysed: ', end=" ")
test = []
test.append(input())
test_dtm = trainingVector.transform(test)
predLabel = LR_complete.predict(test_dtm)
tags = ['Negative','Positive']
#Display Output
print('The review is predicted',tags[predLabel[0]])
```

According to the tokens in text it will predict as positive or negative. The tokens are already categorised as negative and positive. Result will be shown as the the review is predicted as positive or negative.

Figure 6: Output

V. CONCLUSION

We gather more data every day, therefore it would be impossible for us to analyse it by simply looking at it. To analyse from such an enormous volume of data, we often use distinct analysis methods. By classifying the reviews as positive or negative, the logistic regression approach is employed to accurately determine the polarity of the reviews in this case. People rely on social networking sites in a world where the internet is highly valued. Analyzing the reviews from these blogs will result in a better knowledge and aid in their decision-making. In order to obtain the most accurate results when predicting reviews, the logistic regression algorithm was applied among other machine learning techniques. Two crucial elements in the prediction were data preparation and collecting. This prediction will help analyse and predict the future work using the analysed data.

In this paper, we exclusively analyse the text's negative and positive words. However, we were unable to analyse texts that contained sarcasm in a similar context. Therefore, in the future, we will attempt to integrate sarcasm as well using alternative effective algorithms. Consequently, this will aid in preventing the analysis of misleading information.

VI. REFERENCES

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